

Table 1. Comparative characteristics of training goals, focus and indicative load by age group in wrestling

Age group	Primary goals	Main training orientation
8–10 years	Development of basic motor skills and positive engagement in wrestling	Broad motor and coordination development; playful introduction to stance, movement, safe falling and simple grips; emphasis on enjoyment, safety and socialisation
11–13 years	Formation of basic technical skills and movement control	Consolidation of fundamental techniques in standing and par terre; gradual increase of general strength and endurance; structured but still varied drills; low-pressure “learning” competitions
14–15 years	Development of physical qualities and technical combinations	Targeted development of strength, speed and special endurance; systematic work on combinations and counters; more situational drills and controlled sparring; introduction of basic psychological skills (goal-setting, coping with pre-start anxiety)
16–17 years	Preparation for higher-level competition and mental readiness	Integration of individual technical–tactical systems; more individualised strength and conditioning; regular national-level competitions; structured mental preparation (focus, emotional self-regulation, post-match analysis)
18+ years (junior/senior)	Optimisation of high-performance results and long-term career sustainability	Highly individualised, competition-specific preparation; micro-periodisation of loads; technical–tactical refinement based on match analytics; systematic injury prevention, recovery and psychological support